

GEOMORPHOLOGICAL AND MITIGATING INTERPRETATION OF SINDORO VOLCANO USING SATELLITE IMAGERY

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Abstract

Indonesia is an archipelagic country with a volcanic spread of 127 volcanoes. The subduction zone of the Indo-Australian plate and the Eurasian plate formed the formation of the volcano in Central Java province. The volcano eruption in the past has had a positive and negative impact. Some positive impacts from the eruption can make more fertile soil from the removal of volcanic ash material. One of the negative impacts of volcano are destruction of surrounding environment and human disaster. Identification of volcanic landform is needed to increase the mitigation of volcanic eruption disaster. Landform identification has discussed by using remote sensing and satellite imagery. This paper aims to perform the analysis landform of Sindoro Volcano. Based on satellite imagery, the results of the analysis show 13 landforms on Sindoro Volcano. The results of the interpretation of volcanic landforms of Sindoro Volcano, there are 1 crater, 1 lava dome, 3 volcanic cones, 4 parasitic cone volcanoes, 3 volcanic ridges, and 1 plain of volcano. The interpretation must be confirmed by observation on field to produce the form of Sindoro Volcano in more detail.

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1. Introduction

Indonesia is an archipelago which is also passed by an active volcano way (Ring of Fire). Data from BMKG (the Meteorology, Climatology and Geophysics Agency) in 2013 noted that Indonesia had 127 active volcanoes. The presence of volcanoes has many impacts on people's lives, both positive and negative impacts. One of the positive effects is the release of volcanic ash material which can help soil fertility. One of the negative impacts of volcanoes is volcanic eruptions cause casualties and temporarily damage the environment caused by lava flows and pyroclastic which have very high temperatures. Based on the results of the statistical data summarized by the BNPB (National Disaster Management Agency), the number of victims due to volcanic eruptions from 1815 to 2018 recorded 78,639 fatalities (dead and missing) in Indonesia. Another negative impact that can occur with the presence of volcanoes is the existence of steep slope morphology. It can trigger the landslides. BNPB noted that landslides are the number three natural disaster that often occurs in Indonesia, and in early 2018 it was the largest casualty.

Based on high negative impacts, it is necessary to have a recent analysis of sindoro volcanoes to update the Sindoro Volcano mitigation identification. Volcano mitigation analysis in the form of eruption patterns history and landforms produced so as to minimize casualties

which are caused by activities of the sindoro volcano. The purpose of the landscape and landform analysis of Sindoro Volcano is to be able to provide an overview of disaster-prone areas, so as to provide a consideration for the community in determining the point of settlement development.

2. Theory

Volcano is both the places or opening from which molten rocks or gas, and generally both, issue from the earth's interior onto the surface, and the hill or mountain built up around the opening by accumulation of the rocks material (MacDonald, 1972). Based on Vulcanology survey Indonesia (VSI), Sindoro Volcano classified as Stratovolcano type that has effusive and explosive eruption type which erupts alternately.

Geomorphology is study of landform and processes which affects it forms and studied between the forms and processes in spatial order (Van Zuidam, 1979). Landform is terrain appearance that formed by natural processes which has specific composition and physical characteristic. Brahmantyo and Bandono (2006) has the landscape and landform classification that used in this research. The primary principal used in this classification is the classification of 1:25.000 scaled map and based on geological factor that observed from topography map, aerial imagery, satellite image, or morphological observation in the field. Geomorphology units classification classified by three or four words principal with special cases for example forms/geometry/morphology, morphological genesis (Endogenous and exogenous process), and geographical name. in this classification, volcanic landform known as ridge. BMB classification classify landform into 9 classes, ridge folds, Plateau ridge, ridge faults, volcanic ridge, karst mountains, fluvial and lake flatland, coast flatland, marine & deltaic, desert, and glacial. Based on Brahmantyo and Brandono, Volcanic landscape classified into 18 type of landform (Figure 1).

Landslide is one of soil and rock movement, or mixing between soil and rock, sliding down the slope because of disturbed soil stability or rock forming it slope. (UU no 24 Tahun 2007).

Landslide depend of the complex interaction between interconnected factors. These factors can be classified into two categories, first causative factor, for example percent of slope, type of rocks, elevation, soil properties, and land cover. The other factor is trigger factor, for example high rainfall, earthquake, glacier bursts, and volcanic activity (Dai et al, 2003).

3. Location of Research

The research location located in Sindoro Volcano area with the highest elevation is ± 3150.7 meters above sea level. Sindoro Volcano is administratively located in two districts, Temanggung Regency and Wonosobo Regency, Central Java Province. Geographically, Mount Sindoro located on coordinates of $7^{\circ} 18' 00''$ South Latitude and $109^{\circ} 59' 30''$ West Langitude.

Figure 2. Location map of research area

4. Methods

This research was conducted with remote sensing methods, field observation methods, and literature study methods. Remote sensing methods covering interpretation of visual landform based on satellite imagery available downloaded from SAS Planet software. This research used satellite imagery Bing Maps with magnification up to 21 times. Field observation methods covering geological mapping in the research area to know distribution of lithology and landform in the research area. Literature study methods covering collecting secondary data such as rainfall map, slope map, landslide map, geological map Magelang's sheet, and disaster-prone map of Temanggung district and Wonosobo district. After that, all of the data processed and interpreted become a paper.

5. Result and Discussion

5.1. *Landform Analysis*

Circle form in the center which highest elevation in the research area classified as a unit of the crater eruption jalatunda (area 1). From satellite imagery, crater landform interpreted based on a morphological form circular depression, the bright white color and the walls in the crater has a relative rough texture was interpreted based on vulcanic material that has been altered due to contact with the sulfur gases was released by volcanic activity. In addition, to the West and North of the crater there is a plain landform with a relatively smooth texture. In this landform hardly to found vegetation as found on slopes up to the plain of the volcanic. This unit has the eruption in all directions particularly Southwest and Northeast.

Around the crater contained morphology seemed obtrusive and classified as a Lava dome Sindoro (area 2) with the direction of the flow toward the North and East. Land form lava dome based on satellite imagery in the research area can be recognized from a relatively convex morphology, the texture is a bit rough, bright brown color, vegetation can found relatively farther from the center of the eruption area.

If it is seen more clearly, the research area also has a circular form that can be classified into the cone of Mount Sindoro volcanic unit (area 3), the cone of mount sumbing vulcanite unit (area 12) and the cone of mount tlerep (area 13). Based on topographic maps, the third area that has circular contours patterns and concentrates with relative space tenous to very close and the elevation is getting into the higher. It indicates the cone morphology volcano. Cone vulcano land form is the morphology of the volcano was formed by the repetition of the process of eruption that occurred in the past. Based on slope and distance relative to the center of the eruption, Cone Sindoro vulcano in the research area can be distinguished a two-part landform are the upper slope and lower slope. the upper slope has steep slopes to very steep, texture in general is relatively rough, dark green-dark green, vegetation starts to be found a lot, general texture is relatively smooth, brown and green, vegetation is not as much as on the upper slopes, residential and agricultural land began to grow. In addition there are two cones found in the research area. Landform Sumbing vulcanic cones found in the southeast of the research area and located in the lower slope of the landform. Landform Tlerep vulcanic cone found in the north-west of the research area covers the upper slope to the lower slope.

In addition, circular shapes with smaller geometries can found generally on the slope of the main volcanic cones classified into vulcano parasitic cone unit including kembang vulcano parasitic cone (area 4). Kekep vulcano paracitic cone (area 5), Watu vulcano paracitic cone, dan Arum vulcano paracitic cone (area 7). From the topographic map it can be seen that all four areas have the same contour pattern specifically circular and centered ones countour that indicate vulcanic cone morphology. Vulcano parasitic cone in the research area can be divided into four types based on satellite imagery. Kembang vulcano parasitic cone is located in southwest of the main volcanic cone. This landform is a volcano parasitic cone with biggest dimension more than other vulcanic parasitic cone. In satellite imagery shows relatively smooth texture, color is dominant dark green with vegetation is relatively abundant. Kekep parasitic cone located on the west side of Kembang vulcano parasitic cone. in satellite imagery has texture relative more rough if compared with main volcanic parasitic cone, and have dark green color. Arum vulcanic parasitic cone located is really close to Kembang parasitic cone on the north side of the volcano. In satellite imagery has texture rough and dark green color. Watu

vulcanic parasitic cone located on the south of the research area. In satellite imagery has a rough texture, and dark green color.

Besides the circular form, there is also a form of ridge found in the several location. This landform covering Watu lava flow ridge (area 9) dan kekep lava flow ridge (area 8), and Sindoro pyroclastic ridge (area 10). Vulcanic landform is a landform with very unique appearance in the satellite imagery. Watu lava flow rich can found on the south from the research area and really close to Watu parasitic cone volcano. This landform has texture relatively rough, has dark green color, and can differentiated really clearly with other morphology in the lower slope around it. Kekep lava flow ridge can found on the southwest and west of the research area. If it is compared to Watu lava flow ridge, this landform has a texture very smooth, dark green color in the satellite imagery. Sindoro pyroclastic ridge also has very unique appearance that is morphological formation resembling a back. Textures tend to smooth-rough and dark green color in the satellite imagery.

The last landform is a Sindoro Sumbing volcano plain (area 11) on the southeast of the research area. From topographic map, this area interpreted as plain because the tenuous contour pattern and the location between two volcanic cones. Sindoro Sumbing plain is one of the easily observed landform form the satellite imagery. Beside the slope that tend to be flat, this landform also has a smooth texture, vegetation begin to decline, settlements, agricultural land roads begin to develop.

Figure 3. Landforms map of Sindoro Vulcano

5.2. Mitigation

Awareness of the enormous negative impacts caused by the natural disasters of the Sindoro Mountain in the form of volcanic eruptions or landslides make the most recent mitigation analysis needed. One of the mitigation efforts is making a map of disaster-prone areas. In making a map of disaster-prone areas based on the parameters of rainfall map, slope map, Magelang's sheet geological map, and landslide-prone map.

Based on the scoring results from 4 parameters used, the research area can be divided into 4 regional zones.

5.2.1. *Safe zone.* This area has the characteristic of low rainfall level (51 mm-100 mm), according to BMKG data in 2018. Besides that it has a degree of slope with an average percent slope of 8% -15%. The next parameter is the geological map with its region formation of Sindoro volcano formation. In addition, based on the landslide map, Sindoro Volcano is included in the low potential zone of landslide, according to data from ESDM in 2018. Based on the geomorphological analysis, this area is consisted of dominating landforms in the form of plain volcanic (pyroclastic fall deposits and Sumbing volcanic products), volcanic cone (lithology consist of andesite lava, basaltic lava, and pyroclastic deposits), lava flow ridge (andesitic lava flow), and pyroclastic flow ridge (pyroclastic flow deposits)

5.2.2. *Moderate zone.* This area has the characteristic of low rainfall level (51 mm-100 mm). Besides that it has a slope which tends to be quite steep with an average slope of 15% - 25%. The next parameter is a geological map with the region formations of Sindoro Volcano formation. In addition, based on the landslide map, Sindoro Volcano is included in the moderate potential landslide zone, according to ESDM data in 2018. Based on geomorphological analysis, this area is consisted of dominating landforms of volcanic cone (lithology consist of andesite lava, basalt

lava, and pyroclastic deposits) and pyroclastic flow ridge (pyroclastic flow deposits).

Figure 4. Disaster-prone map of Sindoro Vulcano.

5.2.3. *High Risk Zone.* This area has the characteristic of low rainfall level (51 mm-100 mm). Besides that it has a slope which tends to be quite steep with an average slope of 25% - 45%. The next parameter is a geological map with the region formation of Sindoro Vulcano formation. In addition, based on the landslide map, Sindoro Vulcano is included in the high potential landslide zone. Based on geomorphological analysis, this area is consisted of dominating landforms of parasitic cone (basalt lava) and volcanic cone (lithology consist of andesite lava, basalt lava, and pyroclastic deposits).

5.2.4. *Very High Risk Zone.* This area has the characteristic of low rainfall level (51 mm-100 mm). Besides that it has a slope which tends to be quite steep with an average slope of >45%. The next parameter is a geological map with the region formation of Sindoro Vulcano formation. In addition, based on the landslide map, Sindoro Vulcano is included in the high potential landslide zone. Based on geomorphological analysis, this area is consisted of dominating landforms of lava dome (andesitic lava), parasitic cone (basalt lava) and eruption center (active crater that emits solfatara gas).

6. Conclusion

Based on the genetic aspect, the geomorphology of the study area is classified into 13 geomorphology units. There are Jalatunda Eruption Crater, Sindoro Lava Dome, Sindoro Volcanic Cone, Kembang Parasitic Cone, Arum Parasitic Cone, Kekep Parasitic Cone, Watu Parasitic Cone, Tlerep Volcanic Cone, Sindoro Pyroclastic Flow Ridge, Watu Lava Flow

Ridge, Kekep Lava Flow Ridge, Sindoro-Sumbing Volcanic Plains, and Sumbing Volcanic Cone. Disaster-prone map of Sindoro Vulcano is divided into 4 regional zones : safe zone, moderate zone, high risk zone, very high risk zone. This map was created from parameters of rainfall map, slope map, Magelang's sheet geological map, and disaster-prone map.

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